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MS17: Prototype of a training catalogue made available to the science clusters with feedback collected on the usability by early adopters

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Milestone MS17, implemented within EVERSE Work Package 5 (Capacity Building and Recognition), marks the availability of the EVERSE Training Catalogue to the science clusters.

This milestone supports early feedback with the training catalogue and enables practical validation of its usability.

The training catalogue provides a structured and centralised view of training resources, including training materials, trainers, and events. It was assessed by a group of early adopters from the clusters, who evaluated its usability and navigation.

The collected feedback provides actionable insights into the user experience and identifies priorities for improvement. These results will directly inform subsequent development iterations, ensuring the catalogue effectively contributes to WP5 objectives by supporting capacity building and fostering wider adoption across the science clusters.

1. Overview of the Training Catalogue Prototype

1.1. EVERSE Training

EVERSE Training (<https://everse-training.app.cern.ch/>) is an open-source training catalogue providing resources and events to support early career scientists and research software engineers (RSE) on best practices in scientific software engineering. The goal of the platform is twofold: first, it is a one-stop-shop for trainees to discover and learn from a list of curated content; and second it provides recognition for trainers and training content providers from different science clusters.

The EVERSE Training infrastructure is currently hosted and maintained at CERN. The list of training materials is a collaborative effort between members of WP5 (see “D5.2 Enhanced and Curated Training Resources Aligned with Software Best Practices: Initial release”, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17233228>).

The screenshot shows the EVERSE Training homepage. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the logo and links for Materials, Events, Trainers, About, and Log in. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- Training and events to foster Research Software Quality:** A large heading with a sub-heading. Below it, a brief description: "Browse the catalogue and find local and online courses, events, as well as videos, presentations, tutorials ... All types of resources at all levels for leveraging Research Software Quality."
- Upcoming events:** A list of two events:
 - Research Software Quality Across Continents:** Face-to-face, 14 April 2026 @ 08:00 - 13:15.
 - Gray Scott School 2026:** Hybrid, 22 June - 3 July 2026.
- Search bar:** A search input field with the placeholder text "Search EVERSE Training..." and a magnifying glass icon.
- Latest materials:** A section featuring a course titled "Tillburg ScienceHub: README Best Practices" with tags for "README", "markdown", and "template".
- Featured trainer:** A section featuring two trainers:
 - Céline Acary-Robert:** A scientific computing research engineer working in an applied mathematics lab and also in the computing mesocenter in Grenoble. Location: Laboratoire Jean Kuntzmann / GRICAD 150 Pl. du Torrent, 38400 Saint-Martin-d'Hères France.
 - Maximilian Linhoff:** The Lead Developer of the Data Processing and Preservation System at the Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory. Location: Dortmund, Germany.

Figure 1. EVERSE Training homepage provides information about upcoming events as well as the search bar as first seen elements in the page. When scrolling down, latest materials and descriptions from featured trainers are shown.

1.2. Choosing the Right Software for implementing the Training Catalogue

The training catalogue is based on the open-source TeSS platform (Training e-Support System) which has been developed and extensively used for many years by ELIXIR (i.e., more than four thousand materials and fifteen thousand past events in 2026). Other institutions have chosen TeSS as their training catalogue, such as the Photon and Neutron sciences (PaN Training, <https://pan-training.tesshub.hzdr.de/>), the Dutch research data (Taxila, <https://taxila.nl/>), the Digital Research Alliance of Canada (Explora, <https://explora.alliancecan.ca/>) and the High Energy Physics (HEP Training, <https://training.cern.ch/>) to cite a few. The currently running OSCARS mTeSS-X Project (<https://elixirtess.github.io/docs/overview/mtess-x/>) overcomes the fragmentation of training resources across Research Infrastructures and the European Science Clusters by allowing the free exchange of training materials and events between TeSS instances.

The choice of using TeSS has also been influenced by the fact that the TeSS platform is “committed to the FAIR principles” (<https://elixirtess.github.io/docs/developers/code-data/>) and that the software is open-source, thus open to contributions (<https://github.com/ElixirTeSS/TeSS>). The latter allows a pool of features we had pick up to meet our requirements, further detailed below (Section 1.3). Moreover, it allows us to develop custom functionalities to tailor them to the needs of our users.

1.3. Requirements

The EVERSE Training catalogue needed to meet several requirements:

- The catalogue must display and showcase to users the curated resources from an internal list of training materials, and it must automatically update training resources to allow its scaling and to reduce the amount of manual work required to populate the catalogue.
- The catalogue must incorporate its training resources seamlessly within other EVERSE services, such as the RSQKit.
- The catalogue must have a way to reward trainers and training content providers.

2. Main Features of the Catalogue

2.1. Materials and Events

The original TeSS platform offers a broad catalogue of features (<https://elixirtess.github.io/docs/content/manual/>). To avoid cognitive overload, we decided to only include the Materials and Events (and Trainers, see [Trainer's Profiles](#) section).

Figure 2. ELIXIR TeSS homepage. The similarity with EVERSE Training is the search bar at first sight. In the ELIXIR TeSS version, there are other features who are not shown in EVERSE Training such as the e-Learning, Workflows, Collections and Learning paths (to see more: <https://elixirtess.github.io/docs/overview/definitions/>).

The current catalogue displays a list of curated materials from a GitHub repository (see 3 in the D5.2, <https://zenodo.org/records/17233228>). The catalogue has thus the functionality to automatically harvest all content available in a specific GitHub repository and to format it into training materials in the interface. The catalogue also can read and import events from indico categories. This content curation is currently provided by members of WP5.

2.2. Widgets and integration with other services

The Research Software Quality Kit (RSQKit, <https://everse.software/RSQKit/>), another EVERSE service, provides a list of curated best practices in developing, collaborating on and improving the quality of research software. Among multiple topics, the platform lists a set of common tasks for following good practices in research software engineering. It is meant to act as the first encounter with EVERSE and as the main resource for Research Software Engineers or Researchers.

TeSS is offering widgets to incorporate to other web pages through a simple HTML code. This allows any web page to display a subset of relevant training materials through a specific search query (https://elixirtess.github.io/TeSS_widgets/).

EVERSE Training is leveraging on this feature to allow the integration of its training materials with most of RSQKit tasks' pages.

2.3. Trainer's profiles

EVERSE Training can also showcase a list of trainers, each of them having their own personal page that can be customized with information such as the training experience, the academic and technical expertise, interests and activities. This profile also provides the list of materials and events registered on the platform. The goal of these profiles is to recognize the work and contributions one has made for the community and education.

3. Feedback Collection Methodology and Results

3.1. Feedback Collection Methodology

Usability feedback was collected from early adopters using a mixed-method combining structured questionnaires and qualitative input.

The methodology involved [EVERSE General Assembly Meeting \(GAM\)](#) sessions, complemented by email outreach to scientific clusters, to determine the total number of participants.

To accommodate different user preferences and maximise participation, two formats were made available:

- ▶ A [GitHub issue template](#), designed around the 10 questions of the Standard System Usability Scale (SUS), enabling respondents to provide both ratings and comments.
- ▶ A [LimeSurvey form](#), offering an alternative channel with the same Standard System Usability Scale (SUS) -based questions to ensure consistency across responses.

Participants were encouraged to interact with the Training Catalogue by performing representative tasks such as trainer profile creation, materials and event submission, and discovery.

In addition to written responses, oral feedback was gathered during an on-site session at the [EVERSE General Assembly Meeting \(GAM\)](#) and documented by the WP5 team.

To broaden engagement beyond the event, targeted outreach was conducted via email in collaboration with WP4, reaching pilot science clusters and inviting them to contribute feedback using either of the two formats.

Each statement in the System Usability Scale (SUS) is rated on a 1–5 scale, ranging from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree”. For the additional feature-related questions, responses are rated from “Not at all” to “Extremely well” to describe the functionality of the features.

The SUS questions and the additional feature-related questions were classified by theme for the analysis:

▶ **Ease of Use and Learnability**

Questions 1, 3, 7, 10 from the SUS

“I think that I would like to use this system frequently”

“I thought the system was easy to use”

“I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly”

“I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system”

▶ **System Complexity**

Questions 4, 8, 2, 6

“I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system”

“I found the system very cumbersome to use”

“I found the system unnecessarily complex”

“I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system”

► User Confidence

Question 9

"I felt very confident using the system"

► Feature-Oriented Feedback

Feature-related responses included SUS question 5 and additional non-SUS questions aimed at evaluating system functions.

"I found the various functions in this system were well integrated"

"Would you like to be able to rate the materials and/or select your favorites?"

"How do you rate the registration process of a new material?"

"How do you rate the registration process of a new event?"

"How do you rate the registration process of a new trainer?"

"Would you like to have a chatbot to help you find the right course for you?"

"How do you rate the connection from the RSQKit to the Training Catalog?"

"How well does this tool meet the specific needs of your research community?"

This grouping allows identification of specific feature strengths, independently of general usability.

► Qualitative Feedback

Comments

"What did you like most about the system?"

"What aspects need the most improvement?"

"Any other comments or suggestions?"

3.2. Usability Feedback Results

3.2.1. GitHub & LimeSurvey Feedback

Usability feedback was collected from eight early adopters via GitHub Issues, including two participants who provided oral feedback, one who provided only oral feedback, and three participants via LimeSurvey, using the dedicated [EVERSE Training Catalogue usability template](#).

Among them:

- 3 participants explicitly identified with the **ESCAPE** cluster
- 1 participant with **PaNOSC**,
- 1 from **EOSC-Life**
- 2 from **ENVRI**
- 4 participants did not specify a cluster.

Total responses: 12

GitHub issues, as well as LimeSurvey responses and results, are available in the following repository: [LimeSurvey results](#) ; [GitHub issues](#)

► Ease of Use and Learnability

Overall, participants reported a generally positive perception of ease of use and learnability.

A clear majority expressed favourable opinions: 8 participants agreed or strongly agreed that **they would like to use the system frequently**, while 2 participants selected a neutral response, indicating neither clear satisfaction nor dissatisfaction. Only 1 participant disagreed, suggesting usability concerns among a small minority.

Similar trends were observed for **perceived ease of use**, with 8 participants agreeing, 2 participants remaining neutral, and 1 participant disagreeing.

For learnability, most respondents felt that the system can be learned quickly: 7 participants agreed or strongly agreed **that most people would learn to use the system rapidly**. However, 1 participant remained neutral, and 3 participants disagreed or strongly disagreed, highlighting that learnability may not be equally straightforward for all users and could depend on prior experience or expectations.

Finally, the learning effort required before getting started was viewed very positively. A strong majority of 10 participants disagreed or strongly disagreed **with the statement that they needed to learn many things before using the system**, while 1 participant selected a neutral response.

Overall, these results indicate that **the system is perceived as “Very easy to use”**, while also pointing to opportunities to further improve early guidance for users.

► System Complexity

Overall, perceptions of system complexity were largely positive, with most participants rejecting **the idea that the system is complex** or cumbersome. For the assessment of whether the system felt cumbersome to use, 9 participants disagreed or strongly disagreed, indicating that the system is generally perceived as manageable, while 2 participants selected a neutral response.

Similarly, most respondents did not consider **the system unnecessarily complex**. 8 participants disagreed or strongly disagreed with this statement, and 2 participants remained neutral.

Regarding **system consistency**, perceptions were again positive. 9 participants disagreed or strongly disagreed with the statement that there was too much inconsistency in the system, while 1 participant selected a neutral response and 1 participant agreed.

The need for external support was perceived as **low** by most participants. A strong majority, 8 out of 11 respondents, disagreed or strongly disagreed with the statement that they would need the support of a technical person to use the system, including 4 who strongly disagreed. This indicates that the Training Catalog is largely seen as accessible without specialised assistance.

However, 2 participants selected a neutral response, suggesting some uncertainty or a potential need for guidance.

Taken together, these results indicate that users generally experience the system as coherent and well structured, while highlighting the importance of maintaining **clear documentation** to support those who may require additional reassurance.

► User Confidence

User confidence while interacting with the system was generally positive, though with some variation across respondents. A **clear majority expressed confidence**: 7 participants agreed

or strongly agreed that they felt confident using the system, including 2 who strongly agreed. This suggests that most users are comfortable navigating and using the catalogue.

At the same time, 3 participants selected a neutral response, indicating neither strong confidence nor lack of confidence, which **may reflect limited exposure or the need for further familiarisation**. Only 1 participant strongly disagreed, representing an isolated case of low confidence.

Overall, the results indicate a solid level of user confidence.

► Feature-Oriented Feedback

Feature-oriented feedback shows a generally positive but still evolving perception of the Training Catalog's functionality, with several responses highlighting both appreciation and areas where experience remains limited due to partial usage.

Regarding **functional integration**, opinions were balanced: 5 participants agreed that the **system's functions are well integrated**, while 5 selected a neutral response, and 1 did not provide an answer. This suggests that while integration is perceived positively by many users, others may not yet have explored enough features to form a clear opinion.

The ability to **rate training materials or select favourites** was largely welcomed. A majority (5 respondents) considered this feature very useful *"I think some level of ordering/ranking would be useful. I searched for git and github (usecase: directing students here to get materials). Git results were lots, but unordered/not ranked. Searching for github gave unclear results as to which was best. So, ranking would help."*, while a smaller number viewed it as moderately useful (1) or nice to have (1). One participant indicated it was not needed, and 3 did not respond, reflecting differing expectations but an overall interest in **content evaluation** and **personalisation features**.

Feedback on **the potential use of a chatbot to help find courses** was also broadly positive. 5 participants rated it as very useful, 2 as moderately useful, and 1 as nice to have, while 3 provided no response. This indicates interest in guided discovery, although **it is not seen as essential by all users**.

Responses related to **the connection between RSQKit** and the Training Catalog were limited, with 7 participants not responding, suggesting insufficient exposure to this feature. Among those who did respond, opinions were mixed: 1 rated the connection as good, 1 as excellent, and 2 reported it as poor or unreliable, **highlighting the need for further clarification and more detailed coverage of the RSQkit content (task pages)** *"is it possible also to have a link back to RSQkit (to the various things covered there)? Maybe also as an own TeSS resource for each RSQkit task page?"*.

Similarly, feedback on registration workflows was constrained by limited usage.

For **material** registration, 2 respondents rated it as good, while 9 did not provide feedback. For **event** registration, 3 rated the process as good, with 8 non-responses.

The **trainer** registration process received 3 positive ratings, 1 indicating partial functionality, and 7 non-responses.

This suggests that many users have not yet interacted with these features, particularly because these actions require creating or adding content, which **could not be completed in time by participants responding to the questionnaire** *"I'll probably need to spend more time reviewing this to give better feedback."*. The evaluation may therefore require feedback from users who have already attempted to add materials. This was the case for one participant, who had previously added a real event, while the others (the majority) had trainer profiles and were familiar with the action before rating it. However, adding materials proved more difficult **within the available timeframe, whether during the GAM session or via email**.

Finally, when asked **how well the Training Catalog meets the needs of their research community**, 5 participants provided positive evaluations (3 “well”, 1 “extremely well”, 1 “partially”), while 6 did not respond.

In conclusion, while the Training Catalog already meets the needs of its research community to a reasonable extent, its effectiveness could be significantly improved through better user guidance, enhanced search and ranking and clearer RSQKit integration.

► Qualitative Feedback

This section presents the comments received from participants, some of which have already been referenced in the previous sections.

What did you like most about the system?

“Very easy to use,”

“I liked the depth of content.”

“The fonts are large, and the layout is easy for readers to find information.”

What aspects need the most improvement?

“We need more and well curated content”

“Clear link to high-quality, frequently accessed training materials. Not just the latest added ones.,”

“On the front page, it might be good to show some highlights from recent events.”

“I think some level of ordering/ranking would be useful. I searched for git and github (usecase: directing students here to get marterials). Git results were lots, but unordered/not ranked. Searching for github gave unclear results as to which was best. So, ranking would help.”

Any other comments or suggestions?

“I’ll probably need to spend more time reviewing this to give better feedback.”

“Almost all materials have no license specified. This is important to include for reusability”

“Is it possible also to have a link back to RSQkit (to the various things covered there)? Maybe also as an own TeSS resource for each RSQkit task page?”

“I see that there is only one provider of training material EVERSE, where actually there is content from e.g. HSF and Carpentries, does this need to be changed”

3.2.2. Oral Feedback

In addition to the LimeSurvey questionnaire and GitHub issues feedback, oral feedback was collected during discussions with early adopters while exploring the Training Catalogue during the GAM.

This feedback complements the survey results by highlighting concrete usage questions, expectations, and areas for improvement that may not be fully captured by the SUS structured questionnaires.

Participants highlighted the need for **clearer descriptions** and **documentation** explaining how such integrations work, including how external resources are ingested, referenced, and maintained within the Training Catalogue.

Several comments also focused on **the limitations of the current filtering options**. Participants expressed the need for a **country-based filter** to better identify geographically relevant training

events, as well as richer and **more expressive filters** to support discovery and **comparison (Ranking) of training resources**.

A substantial part of the oral feedback concerned **metadata quality and transparency**. Participants requested clarification on which metadata schema is used for training materials and how metadata fields are defined. Highlighting that better-defined metadata would improve both discoverability and trust in the content.

Several questions were raised regarding **content provenance and attribution**. Participants noted that training materials currently appear to be provided under EVERSE, which was also highlighted in the survey responses *“I see that there is only one provider of training material EVERSE, where actually there is content from e.g. HSF and Carpentries, does this need to be changed”* highlighting the importance of **clearer attribution** and improved **visibility of content providers** within the catalogue.

Issues related to **trainer representation** were also identified. There is currently **no clear link between courses and their associated trainers**. Users suggested that trainers could be linked to new materials or events, which would improve transparency and engagement.

Finally, some participants explicitly stated that **LLM-based features**, such as chatbots or AI-driven course recommendations, **are not currently required for the Training Catalogue**. Instead, **priority should be given to strengthening content quality, metadata completeness, and filtering capabilities**. This feedback reflects a preference for consolidating foundational features before introducing more advanced automation.

4. Conclusion

With this milestone and the successful deployment of the EVERSE Training Catalogue prototype, built on the robust and FAIR-compliant TeSS platform, EVERSE has made one more step forward to its mission to enhance capacity building and recognition within the research software community. The feedback collected from early adopters across multiple science clusters has been instrumental in identifying the catalogue’s strengths and areas for improvement. Moving forward, the insights gained from this milestone will guide the next iterations of the Training Catalogue. Priorities include expanding and curating content, improving search and ranking mechanisms, and strengthening metadata quality to enhance discoverability and trust.